

Image processing methods for morphological characterization of biomass smoke particles

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INTRODUCTION

- Biomass burning particulate matter (PM) has **varied morphology** and thus, is difficult to measure. Microscopy is a common tool used to help with the composition analysis of biomass samples [1,2].
- Earlier evidence on biomass smoke PM highlights the existence of dark, near-spherical particles with sharp edges known as **tarballs** in relatively high frequencies (~30-45% according to [3,4]).
- Other types observed include soot, ash, minerals, K- and S-rich compounds, and organics [5].
- Ambient conditions play a key role in morphology of aged biomass PM. In particular, the day- and night-time aging are shown to be different due to the reactions being governed, respectively, by OH radicals and NO_x [6].
- To study the composition of samples, the manual image analysis methods are time- and effort-taking and are not usually applied on large datasets. Here, we introduce a fast automated method for morphological analysis of microscopic images and identification of particle types.

METHODS

- Samples for Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) were collected in July 2021 from Kamloops, BC near a forest fire using thermophoretic sampling.

- Randomized imaging was performed on the samples to select particles for morphological analysis.
- Summary of test conditions for the two samples of interest studied here:

Date	Start time	Duration (hr)	Mean PM2.5 (µg/m ³)	Image counts	Particle counts
July 21	18:48 pm	9	31.5	75	737
July 22	10:41 am	1.5	117.4	30	408

- Particles were **segmented** from the image backgrounds using *k*-means clustering [7].

- Morphological analysis** included calculating shape (circularity— or *c*), darkness (relative optical depth— or *z_{opt}*) and sharpness (relative boundary accuracy— or *s_{opt}*) metrics for the segregated particles.

$$c = \frac{2\sqrt{\pi A}}{p} \quad \bar{z}_{opt} = \frac{I_{bg} - I_{par}}{I_{bg}} \quad \bar{s}_{opt} = \frac{|\nabla I_{edg}|}{|\nabla I_{in}|}$$

with *A* projected area, *p* perimeter, and *I* pixel intensity.

- Particles were also labeled by the operator (**manual categorization**) based on the morphological type visually perceived from the images.

RESULTS

- TEM imaging showed a variety of particle types existing in the samples.

- An interesting observation from the night sample was the appearance of a large group of near-round grey blurry particles, looking like organics from the earlier studies, which we named here as **softballs** for brevity.
- The manual analysis of particle types highlighted a significant difference in the morphologies for the day and night samples, presumably due to different aging processes the samples underwent.

- k*-means performed sufficiently in capturing particle outlines for most particles except occasional inaccuracies for the cases with highly diffusive boundaries.

- The metrics chosen, overall, qualitatively followed the operator's visual perceptions. In particular, a sharp gradient in intensity could be captured near the edges of tarballs.
- Within the softballs, on the other hand, the intensities were as noisy as the background.

- The bivariate scatterplots of morphological properties confirm the manually detected distinction between the day and night samples.

- Boundary sharpness seems to be a reasonable metric to distinguish tar- and softballs.
- The partial overlapping in the sharpness of tar and soft populations may be due to different factors, such as formation of hybrid structures, inaccuracies in *k*-means boundary capturing, image noise, misclassification by the operators, etc.
- Softballs were on average smaller and shifted in the night samples ($\bar{d}_a|_{day} = 165 \text{ nm}$, $\bar{d}_a|_{night} = 129 \text{ nm}$). Both tar- and softballs showed a distribution of sizes.
- Both samples had quite high average circularities, as both classes contained near-spherical particles ($\bar{c}|_{day} = 0.94$, $\bar{c}|_{night} = 0.91$).
- Optical depth gave a wide range of variations in both cases with tars showing higher values as expected ($\bar{z}_{opt}|_{day} = 0.52$, $\bar{z}_{opt}|_{night} = 0.37$). These are consistent with the earlier findings on the dependence of mass-absorption cross section on the organic aerosol-to-black carbon ratio, a ratio which, in turn, can vary with the lifetime of emissions [8].

- The confusion matrices for sharpness of the night samples indicates that many particles are accurately classified by this method ($\bar{c}|_{cut-off} = 0.8$, $\bar{s}_{opt}|_{cut-off} = 2.0$).

Real		Predicted Tarballs		Predicted Softballs	
		TRUE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
Real	TRUE	59.5%	40.5%	94.7%	5.3%
Real	FALSE	5.7%	94.3%	48.6%	51.4%

CONCLUSIONS

- The differences in the atmospheric aging pathways of biomass particulate emissions can result in different morphological distributions.
- Automated image processing methods based on machine learning are capable of detecting particles coming from complex sources like forest fires.
- Image sharpness gives promising outcomes when classifying biomass PM.
- The distributions obtained can also help with the data inversion and post-processing of other measurement techniques.
- Future work should focus on the improvement to particle classification using image sharpness as a calibrating parameter.

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